

LITERALLY STUDY OF ARO ISLAND VILLAGE IN TABIR ULU DISTRICT AND LITERATURE LEARNING PHENOMENON IN SCHOOL

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Abstract

This study aimed to describe the oral literature of the Aro island village, especially the type and function of folk songs and the phenomenon of literary learning in schools, especially in the district of Merangin. This qualitative research aimed to understand the phenomenon of what is experienced by the subject of the study such as behavior, perception, motivation, action and others. The research strategy used was a case study strategy, a research strategy in which the researcher carefully investigates a program, event, activity, process, or group of individuals. Data were collected through observation and Interview. Steps in collecting data from respondents through interview, then classify the data with grouping people's songs accordingly with type and its function, and finally interpret the data. Based on observation and interviews, there were 28 pieces of folk songs. The song of the people is grouped according to its contents so that there are 3 kinds of folk songs that are functioning folk songs, lyrical folk songs and folk singing. The singing of the people also has its own function, the function is to suppress or disturb others, to start the game, to puzzle, to entertain the sad person, and as the social controller. Then, based on observations and interviews on syllabus and teaching materials in schools, the position of literary learning is not balanced with language learning in practice. This occurred because; (1) the lack of literary teaching materials in schools, (2) teachers have difficulty in developing teaching materials and learning methods, (3) the lack of literacy and literary culture.

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1. Introduction

Hutomo (1991) says that *lierly study* is a literature that includes the expression of literary citizens of a culture disseminated and passed down orally (word of mouth). This means that oral literature is a tradition born from the overflow of feelings and thoughts within a particular collective, then spread from generation to generation orally or word of mouth.

Oral literary spreading makes oral literary works that have many different types and forms, one significant difference being the language is used in the delivery. Because each literary work produced has its own characteristics, as well as the literary works in the village of Aro Island, Tabir Ulu district.

Aro Village is a village located in Tabir Ulu Merangin district precisely on Muara Jernih street KM 04. Geographically, this village is bordered by New Medan village in the eastern part and Muara Seketuk village in the west, while in the north it is bordered by the river of Tabir, south of Kerinci Sebelat National

Park (TNKS). The village includes a densely populated village in which there are five hamlets in the village: Batu, Harapan, Tebing Tinggi, Tunggak Bulin and Tanjung Raden villages, approximately two thousand (2000) people live in this village. The population is created various cultures and literature in which one of them is the song of the people.

According to Brunvand (cited in Danandjaya, 1991, p. 141), he mentions '... folklore is one of the genres of folklores composed of words or songs, which circulate orally among certain collectives, in the traditional form, and have many variants.'

Each region has its own culture as well as the village of Aro Island eventhough in reality the people of this village have a solid routine but also they have a high literary work of the people's song. The folk singing of the Aro Island village uses the language of Aro Island, with terms that are only known and understood by the local community.

In Aro Island, people's singing of people is not only as a work of entertaining literature but also as a system of social control. For example as an animal repellent wanted to enter the fields.

*Bureteh beruk
Ditengah lah negeri
Ibo nian hati
Ningok lah adik
Supayuh, jangan lah dimakan
Padi nenek
Kuwaw, kuwaw
Bureteh yo beruk bensou migau
Tampurung butali rutan
Kalau lepeh idak aku migau
nak bakurung ku bagih makan*

Folk Singing above, sing at the time the animals enter the fields. How to sing this song should use a loud voice, with a sad tone. This is so that the animal notices that the owner of the field knows its existence and is in sorrow.

Based on observations of researchers in the village of Aro Island on date 09 - 13 January 2017, the village folk song is almost extinct. This is because *Si Pelaku* (people who know the singing of the people) are elderly and also the absence of *the successor* who can sing the song of this people, other than that the local people are not interested anymore to sing people's songs because they are more interested in listening and singing modern songs or music today. Whereas, the oral literature and its function in the community have unique characteristics; characteristic of certain regional culture. However, the uniqueness is beginning to look faded in the community as well as the educational environment, especially in schools. So it affects the literary pursuit at school. Therefore, it is necessary to study the oral literature of Aro Island village, especially about the shape, type, and function of the people's song.

2. Research Methods

The approach used in this study is a qualitative approach. Moleong (2010, p. 6) states that 'qualitative research is a study that intends to understand the phenomenon of what is experienced by research subjects such as behavior, perception, motivation, action and others.' Research strategy in this research is case study. Case studies are qualitative research strategies in which researchers carefully investigate a program, event, activity, process, or group of individuals (Cresswell, 2013).

This research uses a literal approach to the structural analysis. Prodopo et al. (cited in Jabrohim, 2001, p. 55) explains that 'the method of structural analysis is a method which holds that in itself the literary work is an autonomous structure which can be understood as a unified entity with its interlinked elements of development.' Therefore, to understand its meaning, literary works must be studied on the basis of its own structure, independent of the historical setting, independent of the author's self and intent, and independent of its effect on the reader.

3. Discussions

Based on observations and interviews, there were 28 pieces of people's songs. The folklore was classified based on its contents found as 3 types of folk songs; lyrical folk songs and singing the story. The type of folk song in the village of Aro is the same as the type of folk singing in which Brunvand (cited in Danandjaya 1991) states that some of the people's songs belonging to the people's songs are actually (1) *functional songs*, (b) *lyrcral folksongs*, and (c) *narrative folksongs*.

The folk singing of the Aro island community also has a function, although it has undergone conversion due to several factors. The original function of the singing songs of the people of Aro Island village have several functions, the result of the interview with the informant showed five functions of the people song of Aro island village. The folklore function is to suppress or disturb others, to start the game, to puzzle, to entertain the sad person, and as a social controller. However, not all types of folk songs contained in the Aro island community have the same function as proposed by Hutomo (1991) who explained that in oral literary relations, this interesting song is the text of the song, the text of this song is generally poetic . The functions of this poem (people's poetry) are; (1) as a means of enforcing collective society norms, (2) as a social control, (3) to entertain a sad person; (4) to start a game (eg; *homepage*); (5) to suppress or disturb others (eg; *dang dang tut, window uwa-uwa / who ngentut shot gambling old king*)".

Based on the research findings, this time the people's singing has changed function. The transfer function is caused by; (1) the custom event does not use it anymore, (2) to lull the children and grandchildren to use the flow of music today, (3) singing to the grandchildren is not heard again, (4) perpetrators of old age, and many are senile, (5) the interest of the perpetrator has diminished.

The shifting of the function of folk singing as one among oral literature is also due to the position of literary learning in school. Based on the phenomenon that occurs in schools, especially in Merangin District, it is known that literary learning that is not often ignored by teachers in the learning process. Teachers are more focused in the process of literary learning than literature. In literary teaching materials,

teachers tend to utilize literary works in the form of popular novels. If there is material on oral literature, the teacher chooses to use existing oral literature that is generally documented, such as the proverb and the story of the *Kancil* or *Timun Emas*. As a result, literary learning does not develop, students do not know the literature of their own.

The reasons for the emergence of the phenomenon is due to; (1) the lack of literary teaching materials in schools, such as books on literature, (2) teachers tend to utilize teaching materials that exist in the syllabus, teachers have difficulty developing teaching materials with limited reference and learning media, and (3) lack of literary culture from both teachers and students.

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